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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF PRE-TERM BIRTH TO DOCUMENT THE
DIURNAL IMPACT**¹Dr Zubaida, ²Dr Madiha Amjad, ³Rabia Sajjad¹KGN Teaching Hospital Bannu Township Bannu, ²Avicenna Medical College Lahore,³Government College Women University Madina Town Faisalabad.**Article Received:** August 2019**Accepted:** September 2019**Published:** October 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this research work is to examine the commencement of the contractions of uterine & pre-term birth to record any present diurnal impact.

Methodology: We retrieved the clinical records of patients who got admission with identification of pre-term delivery (PD) from May 2014 to June 2018 at Khalifa Gul Nawaz Teaching Hospital Bannu. We noted the onset of the establishment of contraction of uterine of PD, parity and sex of the born child. SPSS V.10 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information.

Results: In the duration of this research work, we recorded total 300 pre-term births. Accurate time of onset of the contraction of the uterine was present in case of 36.30% child births. The contraction of the uterine which led to the labor initiated from 2 AM to 5 AM and about 100 babies were born during early morning or last part of the night (from 8 PM to 8 AM) and delivery of 200 children carried out during day time (from 8 AM to 8 PM). Among all the deliveries during early morning and late night, 45.18% babies were delivered between 2 AM to 8 AM.

Conclusion: Pre-term labors are normally the demonstrator of the diurnal rhythm. In majority of females, the contraction of uterine started 2 AM to 5 AM & majority of the child births occurred from 2 AM to 8 AM.

Keywords: Pre-Term, Contraction, Pregnancy, Uterine, Rhythm, Diurnal.

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INTRODUCTION:

The term Pre-term labor is the commencement of the contraction of uterine with suitable power & rate to impact advanced dilatation & cervix's effacement between twenty to thirty-seven weeks of pregnancy period. There is an estimation that rate of occurrence of the delivery vary with time of the day as well as the time of the year. Concerning the diurnal impacts of the start of labor in females, an obvious peak is present in the night times, although the processes for the finding out the onset deliveries are not present with full explanation, because the contraction of the uterine & oxytocin a hormone for the induction of labor also provides the heavy diurnal rhythms, an important role of the pituitary is prospective. Pre-term labor is the cause of the complications from 3.0% to 8.0% deliveries & it is also one of the most important reason of high rate of morbidity and mortality of neonates. It is very serious problem for the health of the population in terms of lives loss, disability for long durations & high expense for health care in both developed as well developing regions of world.

The data explained that late start of pre-term labor may characterize a physiological process while early pre-term labor is acknowledged pathological process. In the practice of the hospitals, labor times and deliveries times are not in suitable phase with the hours of working. This is particularly vital for pre-term labor as its effectual administration have the ability for the improvement of the outcome of neonates & it have a

positive impact on the expenses of the health care facilities. The aim of this research work is to record the time of commencement of the contraction of uterine when pre-term labor was the cause of child birth as well as the timing of the pre-term child births.

METHODOLOGY:

The duration of this study was from May 2014 to June 2018 and we retrieved the records of hospital of all the patients who got admission for pre-term delivery from Khalifa Gul Nawaz Teaching Hospital Bannu. Ethical committee of the hospital gave the permission to conduct this research work. We obtained the documented time for the commencement of the contraction of uterine. We included only accurate time documented by the physician or staff nurse for analysis. The 1st time for the contraction of the uterine was about nearest to the exact hour. We recorded the time of the start of pre-term labor with the sex of the born baby & parity number of the female. SPSS V.10 was in use for the analysis of the collected information.

RESULTS:

There was a record available of the more than five thousand deliveries in the duration of that research work. A sum of 500 females got admission with the identification for pre-term labor and out of 500, 300 females delivered babies (170 were male & 130 were females). Total 31.48% females were prim-gravid & 22.78% females were multi-gravida as illustrated in Table-1.

Table-I: Parity of Patients with Preterm Labour (n=300)

Parity	Patients	
	No	Percent
Primi Gravida	100.0	31.48
2 nd Gravida	60.0	14.28
3 rd Gravida	50.0	16.28
4 th Gravida	44.0	4.88
Multi Gravida	46.0	22.78

Accurate time of the start of contraction of uterine was present in only 36.30% child births which displays peak in early hours of morning as shown in Figure-1.

Figure 1

In almost all pre-term child births, 100 babies were born during early morning or late hours of night from 8 PM to 8 AM and 200 babies were born in day times

from 8 AM to 8 PM. In all the babies who delivered in the early morning hours, 47.18% were born between 2 AM to 8 AM as illustrated in Figure-2.

Figure-2: Number of women with

Figure 2

DISCUSSION:

The findings of this current work showed that diurnal difference of pre-term labor is present and most of the females delivered their babies early morning hours or late hours of night when there was very low proportion of the professionals were available in the hospital. Therapy & prevention of the pre-term labor is very vital to decrease the adverse outcome of neonate and for the improvement of the survival rate and QoL (Quality of Life). This emphasizes the vitality of the raised presence of the resources during the early morning and late night hours so that suitable administration of the pre-term child births could be under determination. Many countries which are under

development as Pakistan are not able to handle high amount of the healthcare expenses linked with managing newborns that are pre-term, causing in very high rate of the morbidity as well as mortality.

Lindow assessed the four hundred and twenty-five patients of pre-term labor and examined that there was much disparity between amounts of the females who experienced labor during the night times in comparison with the females who delivered in the time of day. Fraser WD discovered that in the females having unprompted start of labor or are membrane rupture before time, there is noticeable diurnal disparities in the admission time in the hospitals. The

rupture of the membrane was much common in the night time in that large sampled study. The top most hours for the child birth were late morning hours or afternoon in that research work. A research work conducted in Switzerland in the year of 2010 by Lerchl, analyzed the dates of birth of more than 3 million babies born from 1970 to 2006 in that country. There was very decrease number of births on weekends. The rising non-availability of the child births on weekends was a result of the reduction of the CS & induction of elective labor which reached in Switzerland to 27.18 & 18.48% correspondingly in the year of 2004.

Goldstick investigated the diurnal impacts of the urgent child birth through surgery & discovered that a positive diurnal rhythm with high rate of frequency was present in normal hours of working. The diagnosis of the pre-term deliveries is very important just like the managing of this issue. In majority of the research works, only 30% to 40.0% females who got admission in hospitals for pre-term labor face a pre-term child birth, signifying a very low positive prognostic value of diagnosis.

Adding fetal fibronectin (FFN) evaluation might take part significantly to diagnose the pre-term child birth. The contraction of the uterine appearing before pain of labor studied utilizing this particular unit which recorded the hourly amount of the uterine contractions which happened before labor from twenty-four weeks onwards. A clear nocturnal increase in the non-labor activity of uterine was present in the research work of Vercoustre L. But, a large sampled research study including about 2500 patients displayed no advantage of HUAM for the prediction of the pre-term labor. Inappropriately, there is change in the prevalence of the pre-term labor over last forty years & reservations still persevere about the best methods for its proper administration.

CONCLUSION:

This research work emphasizes the most vital aspect for the administration of the pre-term child births because majority of females have commencement of labor & resulting deliveries at odd times when there is very meagre availability of the health care facility in the hospitals. There is a requirement to enhance the vigilance at the duration of these odd times by suitable proportion of the fully trained professionals for the proper administration of the pre-term deliveries.

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